

Role of trace elements on the production of L-glutamic acid by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100

S. Ganguly and A. K. Banik*

Department of Chemical Engineering, Biochemical Engineering Division, Bio-Technology Laboratory, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

Manuscript received 27 August 2010, accepted 15 September 2010

Abstract : A study was carried out on the role of different trace elements on the production of L-glutamic acid by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 for the selection of suitable synthetic medium. It was observed that Fe^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were required for this mutant strain. The optimum levels of Fe^{2+} was 5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and both Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} required 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ each for the production of L-glutamic acid. But other elements, namely Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , V^{3+} , Fe^{3+} and Mo^{6+} had an adverse effect on L-glutamic acid accumulation by this strain. Thus, addition of necessary trace elements into the fermentation medium resulted significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in L-glutamic acid accumulation of 23.8 mg/ml compared to the production of this amino acid before addition of necessary trace elements into the fermentation medium (18.8 mg/ml).

Keywords : *Micrococcus glutamicus*, amino acids, L-glutamic acid.

Introduction

Microorganism require specific trace elements for growth and secondary metabolite accumulation like amino acid including L-glutamic acid¹. This requirement varies with the type of microorganism as well as the nature of the basal medium used². Although, there are many reviews on the role of different trace elements on the microbial production of different amino acids. Madhavan *et al.*³ reported that Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} were required for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Brevibacterium roseum*. Hyo Lee *et al.*⁴ obtained L-threonine with a mutant *E. coli* which required Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mo^{6+} . Kinoshita *et al.*⁵ claimed *Micrococcus glutamicus* ATCC 13058 needed Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} for L-glutamic acid production. Sunoda *et al.*⁶ observed that production of L-glutamic acid was elevated many folds in presence of Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} in the fermentation medium by *Brevibacterium flavum* No. 2247. Enshi *et al.*⁷ reported that *Brevibacterium diverticum* required Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Mo^{6+} for the accumulation of L-glutamic acid in the fermentation medium. Banik *et al.*⁸ reported that Fe^{2+} and Mo^{6+} were required for L-methionine production by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* X₁. But Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} had adverse effect on the production of this amino acid by this strain. Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} had almost no

effect on methionine production. Banik *et al.*⁹ claimed that Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} showed positive impact on L-threonine accumulation where as Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} had adverse effect but Mo^{6+} and V^{3+} had almost no effect. Patil *et al.*¹⁰ also supported that production of L-glutamic acid using whole and immobilized cells of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* required Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} .

Considering all these reports, in the present work, an extensive study had been made to find out the trace element requirements for the selection of suitable synthetic medium for L-glutamic acid production by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism : *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100, a biotin requiring auxotrophic mutant, derived from a regulatory mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB1 by induced mutation in our laboratory using UV irradiation as physical and ethyleneimine as chemical mutagen was used throughout the study¹¹.

Minimal salt medium : Minimal salt medium contained glucose, 9.0%; diammonium hydrogen phosphate, 1.4%; dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, 0.15%; magnesium sulfate, heptahydrate, 0.03%; calcium carbonate, 0.04%; biotin, 0.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; pH, 6.5.

Fermentation was carried out using the shake flask method on a rotary shaker (150 rpm) in 100 ml Erlenmayer conical flask containing 20 ml minimal salt medium, for 72 h at 29 °C. The medium was inoculated with 4.0% (v/v) of a 48 h old seed culture (6.0×10^7 cells) of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100.

Addition of trace elements to the basal medium : Initially the basal medium did not contain the trace elements to be investigated. The impurities present in the inorganic salts were further purified by the method of Majumder and Bose¹². The solution of all trace elements prepared in triple glass distilled water, sterilized in autoclave at 15 lbs pressure for 15 min and added separately to the medium to attain the required concentration.

Analysis of amino acid : Descending paper chromatography was employed for detecting L-glutamic acid in culture medium and was run for 18 h on a Whatman No. 1 Chromatographic paper.

Solvent system used include *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (2 : 1 : 1). The spots were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-glutamic acid in the suspension was done using colorimetric estimation method^{13,14}.

Estimation of dry cell weight (DCW) : After centrifugation, a few ml of 1 M HCl was poured into the precipitate of the bacterial cells and calcium carbonate to dissolve calcium carbonate. The remaining bacterial cells were washed with water and dried at 100 °C until cell weight remain constant¹⁵.

Statistical analysis : All data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$. The data were analysed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post-hoc multiple comparison test using "prism 4.0" soft-ware (Graph pad Inc., USA). A "p" value less than 0.05 was considered significant and less than 0.01 was considered highly significant.

Results and discussion

The effect of different trace elements on L-glutamic acid production by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 was depicted in the Figs. 1A-I. Among them Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} showed positive effect on cell growth

Fig. 1A. Role of Cu^{2+} ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; 0.0 stands for control)

Fig. 1B. Role of Fe^{2+} ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1C. Role of Zn^{2+} ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1D. Role of Mn²⁺ (MnSO₄·4H₂O) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1G. Role of V³⁺ (NH₄VO₂) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM. **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1E. Role of Ni²⁺ (NiSO₄·7H₂O) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1H. Role of Fe³⁺ (FeCl₃) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1F. Role of Co²⁺ (CoCl₂·5H₂O) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

Fig. 1I. Role of Mo⁶⁺ (Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O) on L-glutamic acid fermentation and cell growth of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 (where *n* = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01; 0.0 stands for control).

and L-glutamic acid accumulation. Fe^{2+} , 5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; Zn^{2+} , 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; and Mn^{2+} , 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were proved to be the optimum concentrations for L-glutamic acid production by this mutant strain. Other elements studied namely Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , V^{3+} , Fe^{3+} and Mo^{6+} had adverse effect on both cell growth and L-glutamic acid accumulation.

Martin and Daniel¹⁶; Hughes and Poole¹⁷ suggested that those ions probably acted as either activator or inhibitor of some enzymes involved in synthetic steps of metabolites. Hughes and Poole¹⁷ also claimed that even though some toxic metals like Ni^{2+} had detrimental effect on growth and metabolism of microorganisms including bacteria, but in some cases they play some beneficial effect on microorganisms at lower concentrations. However, in our present study we observed that Ni^{2+} showed toxic effect even at lower concentrations on growth and L-glutamic acid accumulation by this mutant.

As a result of the present study, accumulation of L-glutamic acid by this mutant was increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) after addition of required trace elements (23.8 mg/ml) compared to the production of this amino acid by this strain using minimal salt medium without any trace elements studied where it accumulated only 18.8 mg/ml L-glutamic acid.

Thus, from this study, the following suitable synthetic medium was recommended for L-glutamic acid fermentation by the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB100 with a composition of glucose, 9.0%; diammonium hydrogen phosphate, 1.4%; dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, 0.15%; magnesium sulfate, heptahydrate, 0.03%; calcium carbonate, 0.04%; ferrous sulfate, heptahydrate, 5.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; zinc sulfate, heptahydrate, 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; manganese sulfate, tetrahydrate, 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and biotin, 0.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; pH, 6.5.

Acknowledgement

We express our sincere gratitude to the Librarians of Bose Institute, Kolkata; Department of Food Technology and Biochemical Engineering, Jadavpur University, Kolkata and Indian Institute of Chemical Biology (IICB), Kolkata.

References

1. D. D. Woods, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, **30**, 1934.
2. R. D. Sagers and J. V. Beck, *J. Bact.*, 1956, **72**, 199.
3. K. Madhvan, Nampoothiri and A. Pandey, *Biotech. Lett.*, 1996, **18**, 199.
4. L. M. Hyo, L. H. Weon, P. J. Ho, A. J. Oh, J. J. Ki and H. W. Yong II, *J. Biol. Sci. and Bioengg.*, 2006, **101**, 129.
5. S. Kinoshita, K. Tana Ka and S. Akita, US Pat, 300 2 899/ 1961.
6. T. Sunoda, I. Shiio and K. Mitsugi, *J. Gen. Appl. Microbiol.*, 1961, **7**, 18.
7. H. Enshi, H. Nakazawa, S. Okumura and H. Yamada, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1973, **37**, 725.
8. A. K. Banik and S. K. Majumder, *Acta Microbiologica Polonica, Ser. B*, 1975, **7**, 1.
9. A. K. Banik and S. K. Majumdar, *Ind. J. Exp. Biol.*, 1975, **13**, 510.
10. P. M. Patil, N. Gupta, H. Gaudanl, A. Gupta, G. Gupta, V. K. Krishna, S. Trivedi and M. Londhe, *Int. J. Microbiol Res.*, 2009, **1**, 8.
11. S. Ganguly and A. K. Banik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 717.
12. S. K. Majumder and S. K. Bose, *J. Bact.*, 1960, **79**, 564.
13. J. R. Spies, *Methods in Enzymology*, 1957, **3**, 468.
14. F. P. Chinard, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1952, **199**, 91.
15. A. H. Shah, A. Hameed, S. Ahmad and G. M. Khan, *J. Biol. Sci.*, 2002, **2**, 151.
16. J. E. Martine and I. E. Mc. Daniel, *Adv. Appl. Microbiol.*, 1977, **21**, 52.
17. M. N. Hughes and R. K. Poole, Chapman and Hall, USA, 1989, 1-37.